

Peculiarities of the process of forced passportization of Ukrainian citizens in the temporarily occupied territory of Luhansk region

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Abstract

The articles deal with issues of the process of forced “passportization” of Ukrainian citizen in the temporarily occupied territories of Luhansk region. The technologies, forms and methods used by the occupying power of the Russian Federation to strengthen their influence in above-mentioned territories of Ukraine are analyzed.

Key words: passport, occupied territories, Luhansk region, identification of a person.

Introduction

Statement of the problem in general. Forced “passportization” of Ukrainian citizens living in the temporarily occupied territories of Luhansk region, in Russian-inspired quasi-state formation Luhansk People's Republic (LPR) – is a negative trend that threatens Ukraine's sovereignty, strengthens separatists, and does not promote statehood process of Ukraine. The dynamic, forms and methods of issuing passports of the so-called LPR testify numerous scales of this process, and its analysis proves that in this way Russia is trying to increase its

influence in the temporarily occupied territories of Luhansk and Donetsk regions. The situation is complicating in the context of understanding the hidden intentions of the Russian Federation aimed to issuing Russian passports to citizens of Ukraine from the temporarily occupied territories. In this sense, there is a problem in identifying persons who have received new passports of the so-called LPR with new names and have committed to illegal acts and are trying to avoid responsibility.

Material and methods

Among domestic scientists and specialists studying the issue of forced “passportization”, it is worth noting the staff of the National Institute for Strategic Studies, in particular O.O. Reznikov, S.V. Dryomov and representatives of the media sphere, in particular the editor-in-chief of Donbass News Oleksiy Matsuka and the expert of the international and domestic policy program of the Ukrainian Institute of the Future Ihor Tyshkevych. But their materials just touch to the problem of forced “passportization”, of

Ukrainian citizens in the temporarily occupied Donbas.

To the present time, the authors have not found scientific articles devoted to the above-mentioned problem. So, taking into account actuality of the topic authors decided research it.

While writing the article during April-August 2021, one of the co-authors personally managed to communicate with a large number of civilians who crossed the line of demarcation from the temporarily occupied territories of Luhansk

region to Ukraine through the entrance-exit-check-point (EECP) of Stanytsa Luhanska. At the same time, cooperation and close communication with many representatives OSCE Special Monitoring Mission to Ukraine (SMM) helped to understand the perception of the situation through the eyes of the civilian population of Ukraine, who are forced to become citizens of the so-called LPR.

The methodological basis of the study is statistical data on the dynamics of issuance of passports of the Lugansk People's Republic and content analysis of the situation in the

temporarily occupied territory of Luhansk region. The combination of the historical method of cognition of objective reality and the method of political analysis allowed to achieve the goal of the article, which is to study the technology, methods and purpose of forced "passportization" by Russian Federation citizens of Ukraine are living in the temporarily occupied territories of Luhansk region. Documents of the so-called state of the Luhansk People's Republic, in particular passports and tax payer's cards, were used as material carriers of information (for clarity).

Results and discussion

The process of issuing passports of the so-called Luhansk People's Republic to citizens of Ukraine living in the temporarily occupied territories (TOT) of Luhansk region began in May 2015 (U "LNR"). Since then, a significant number of residents of the TOT of Luhansk region have been forced to obtain passports of the so-called LPR. Witnesses (people from occupied territory) said that the occupation authorities, under threat of dismissal, demanded that representatives of the budget professions obtain passports from the so-called Luhansk People's Republic. For several years, a significant number of Ukrainian citizens were forced to obtain passports from authorities of the so-called Luhansk People's Republic without renouncing Ukrainian passports. This is largely due to certain preferences from the Ukrainian passport for residents of TOT Luhansk region (thanks to the Ukrainian passport a person can receive pensions and other social benefits in Ukraine, run a business, receive medical treatment, travel, marry, etc.). At present, it can be reasonably stated that the process of "passportization" of Ukrainian citizens since 2015 and till nowadays in the TOT of Luhansk region is remains forced.

The policy of mass and forced "passportization" of the population of TOT Luhansk region was carried out even in the context of the coronavirus pandemic and has not stopped at present (buses continue to transport people from TOT Luhansk region to

Rostov region in Russian Federation and back on schedule).

The passport of the so-called LPR is issued in the case of: reaching the age of 16 by a person living in the territory of the LPR (Pasport grazhdanina LNR). Thus, not all residents of Luhansk region can obtain passports of the unrecognized republic, but only those who live (registered) in the TOT of Luhansk region.

Before applying for a passport of the so-called LPR, person must undergo fingerprinting or electronic fingerprint scanning. Since October 2019, electronic queue has been implemented for fingerprinting. Hence applier must be beforehand register on the website of so-called state services. Candidates for the LPR passport must be with clear hands and have wet wipes with them. The scan usually takes place in the same building as the passport office in the police station. The work schedule passport office in each district may be different.

The issuance of passports of the so-called LPR is carried out by the Center for Administrative Services in Luhansk (14 Kotsyubynskoho Street).

The procedure for obtaining a passport of the so-called LPR require:

1. Fingerprinting.
2. The presence of a passport of a citizen of Ukraine – the original and a copy of all pages.
3. Birth certificate – original and copy.
4. Marriage certificate – original and copy (in case of divorce or death of one of the spouses – supporting documents originals and copies).

5. Birth certificate of children under 14 years – original and copy.

6. Photo 3.5x4.5 cm with a clear image of the face strictly in full face, without a hat. The size of the image of the oval face in the photo should

be at least 70-80% of the vertical size of the image

7. Receipts for payment in the amount of 200.00 rubles and 80.00 rubles.

8. Application – questionnaire (to be filled in the passport office) (Poluchenie pasporta LNR).

Figure 1,2. The sample of the passport of so-called LPR

Figure 3. The sample of the taxpayer card of so-called LPR

We have to stress that having received the so-called passport of a citizen of the LPR, its owner cannot use it for international travel to European countries and the United States, because the so-called Luhansk People's Republic is only the temporary occupied territory of Ukraine (Oformlenie i poluchenie). Currently, for internal use, the passport of the Luhansk

People's Republic is a necessary condition for the implementation of so-called legal actions in business activities in the TOT of Luhansk region.

A certain feature of passportization in the TOT of Luhansk region is that having received a passport of a citizen of the so-called LPR, the Ukrainian passport document does not need to be handed over (Pasport grazhdanina LNR).

Therefore, having received a passport of the so-called Luhansk People's Republic, residents of TOT of Luhansk region, also having a passport of Ukraine, according to the Law of Ukraine, have the right and opportunity to issue a foreign passport of Ukraine without significant problems. It is also not a problem for Ukrainian citizens who are the residents of the TOT to change the name, which is possible during the marriage.

So, we come to the main core of the article is that the one and the same person from TOT of Luhansk region can possibility to get several passports with different personal data. In other words, such "passportization" has a certain particularity, as it allows a person living (registered) in the temporarily occupied territory of Luhansk region, using the regular procedures to change his name and in some cases citizenship in order to avoid attention from law enforcement agencies.

In this context, it should be noted that young people living in the TOT of Luhansk region according to the state policy of reintegration of Donbas have the opportunity to study on a privilege basis in Ukrainian educational institutions even if a person forced to be a citizen of so called the Luhansk People's Republic. Thus, Ukraine, as a self-sufficient European state, is making significant efforts to support Ukrainian citizens who are forced to live in the territory that is temporarily occupied.

In the context of the above, it should be noted that the compulsory "passportization" of Ukrainian citizens living in the TOT of Luhansk region acquires a new meaning – from June 14, 2019 in Russia began issuing Russian passports to residents of the occupied Donetsk and Luhansk regions. According to media reports, in 2019 more than 196 thousand residents of the occupied Donbas received Russian citizenship in a simplified manner (V Rossij zajavili). Currently, the dynamics are threatening – as of January 2021, more than 400 thousand residents of Donbas received Russian passports (Za rik majzhe), and in May 2021 their number

increased to 530 thousand (Pochty 530 000 zhitilej).

The peculiarity of the above-mentioned passports of the Russian Federation, which are issued to residents of the so-called LPR, is that they have unique identifiers.

First, such Russian Federation passports are issued only in the Rostov region (Novoshakhtinsk and Kamensk-Shakhtinsky).

Secondly, the code of the unit that issues the Russian passport for citizens of the so-called LPR is "610-069" and it is not listed in the register of institutions that issue Russian passports.

Thus, if the passport of the Russian Federation noted that the code of the unit that issued the passport is "610-069" and it is issued in the Rostov region, its owner still probably has a passport of Ukraine and the so-called LPR (because to get a passport of the Russian Federation, residents of TOT Luhansk region are not required to hand over the passport of the so-called LPR).

In the context of the above, it should be noted that the occupying power on the ground sternly requires from state employees (primarily workers, doctors, teachers and representatives of the so-called law enforcement agencies) immediately to obtain Russian passports.

The procedure for issuing Russian passports for residents of the so-called LPR (listed on the website <https://mvdlnr.ru/required-documents.html>, opens via Tor Browser). It provides for the obligatory taking of the oath of a citizen of the Russian Federation. In other words, due to such psychological manipulations, the number of supporters of the concept of "Russian world" is growing.

Specialized business institutions of the Russian Federation provide assistance in obtaining Russian citizenship to residents of the temporarily occupied territories of Donetsk and Luhansk oblasts. In particular, the Moscow legal agency "Migron" specializes in this, which for 6 years has helped to obtain Russian citizenship to 2,500 foreigners, including from the Donbas (Oformlenie i poluchnenie).

Sample passport of the Russian Federation (RF) with identifiers

Sample passport of the RF issued to citizens of the so-called LPR with the corresponding identifiers

Summarizing all mentioned above, it can be noted that a person living in the TOT of Luhansk region on the basis of a passport of Ukraine, can get a passport of the so-called LPR, get married, change his name and get a Russian passport with her new husband's name (as example).

In other words, Ukrainian citizens living in the temporarily occupied territories of Donbass have the opportunity to obtain a Russian Federation passport and travel abroad under a new name in order to hide their identity from the attention of international law enforcement agencies. To this we can add that having a passport of a citizen of Ukraine, a person can

also obtain a passport of Ukraine on his maiden name, because a person may not report his passport manipulations to anyone during his stay in Ukraine.

Potential opportunities for Ukrainian citizens living in the TOT of Luhansk region to obtain passports of the so-called Luhansk People's Republic and Russia (in simplified form) are shown in Table 1. For clarity, the female surname Barvinok is considered, which after marriage is transformed into Ivanova. Note that the process of the above transformation may be reversible.

Table 1 – Obtain passports of the so-called Luhansk People's Republic and Russia (in simplified form)

Last name	Passport of Ukraine	Foreign passport of Ukraine	Passport of LPR	Passport of Russian Federation	Foreign passport of Russian Federation
Maiden name	Barvinok	Barvinok	Barvinok	Barvinok	Barvinok
Surname by husband	Ivanova	Ivanova	Ivanova	Ivanova	Ivanova

According to mentioned above, we can state that the starting point for passport manipulations of persons residing in the TOT of Luhansk region is a passport of Ukraine, which is

the base to get as minimum three different passports with new name different from passports of Ukraine.

Conclusions

1. The analysis of the above material gives to authors grounds to states that “passportization” of Ukrainian citizens living in the TOT of Luhansk region was and remains force. Coercive (force) technologies have administrative nature. The main method of compulsory “passportization” is the method of strict police and administrative supervision for the population living in the TOT of Luhansk region. The purpose of “passportization” of the population on TOT of the Luhansk region consists in attempt of the occupying power of LNR to create a bridgehead for realization of the Russian Federation of the geopolitical intentions on TOT of the Luhansk region.

2. The struggle of the state for the hearts and minds of the citizens of Ukraine living in the temporarily occupied territories of Luhansk region must be continue.

3. International law enforcement institutions must take into account the possibilities of the temporary occupation authorities of Luhansk region regarding their possibility conducting manipulating with passports of Ukrainian citizens.

Prospects for further research – generalization of the experience of compulsory passporization of the population of Ukraine in the temporarily occupied territory of Donetsk region and the Autonomous Republic of Crimea.

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